

Health Care System Reforms and Results in the Case of Kumkurgon District of Surkhandarya Region

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Abstract: *This article describes the progress of reforms in the health sector over the years of independence in our country and in the Surkhandarya region, in particular in the Kumkurgan region, and changes in the field of regional (district) medicine.*

Key words: *health care system, medical sphere, reforms, doctors, district medical association, rural medical centers.*

Relevance of the topic. Fundamentally improving the quality of medical services provided to the population in our country, providing the healthcare system with potential personnel, implementing complex measures aimed at improving the material resource potential of medical institutions has become one of the important strategic tasks in the current pandemic. In his speech at the 75th session of the UN, President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev also emphasized that the above tasks are always important in our country: "From the first days of the registration of COVID-19, we focused all our efforts and resources on curbing this dangerous disease and, most importantly, saving people's lives. In order to mitigate the negative consequences of the pandemic, social protection and health care systems are being dramatically strengthened" [1].

Research methods. The article describes the changes in the health care sector in the years of independence in the Kumkurgan district of the Surkhandarya region on the basis of generally accepted methods - objectivity, historical analysis, comparative-logical analysis, chronological sequence, principles of objectivity.

Research results. In fact, fundamental reforms have been implemented in the health care system in our country, as well as in all areas of our society, and more than 170 legal documents on the reform of the health care sector have been adopted[2]. In this process, important projects are being implemented in order to further improve the medical-prophylactic, patronage support provided to our people, to increase the quality of quick and urgent medical care and specialized medical care, to provide the population with cheap and high-quality medicine, and to develop private medicine.

In particular, it is no exaggeration to say that the decree of the President of December 7, 2018 "On comprehensive measures to fundamentally improve the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [3] has opened a new era in the development of medicine in our country. Thanks to these reforms, a number of important changes in the field of medicine are being implemented in Surkhandarya region.

Specialized clinics equipped with modern medical technologies and equipment occupy an important place in the region's health care system. If in 1991 the rate of maternal death was 65 per 100,000 women, by 2006 this number had dropped to 24. Infant mortality decreased from 35 per 1,000 babies to 14 at the end of 2006. Life expectancy also increased from 67 to 72.5 years. All this was the result of measures aimed at protecting people's health and improving living conditions [4, B. 44-45]. Also, as a result of large-scale work on the prevention of infectious diseases by the mid-1990s, poliomyelitis, typhoid fever,

tetanus, anthrax and highly infectious diseases (cholera, pestilence, etc.) did not occur in Surkhandarya region alone. Salmonellosis decreased by 42 percent, cholera disease by 1.8 times, viral hepatitis by 1.6 times [5, B.8].

In addition, 60 percent of medical institutions in many cities of the region (in the mid-1990s) are located in adapted buildings, so the possibility of fully organizing treatment work is limited [6, B.261].

In 1999-2000, health care in Surkhandarya region improved even more, and the decrees of the President and the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers were consistently implemented. As a result of providing medical institutions with equipment, especially as a result of the establishment of relations with the German company "Simiens", 2 x-ray diagnostic devices of the "Sirokop TsX" model were installed. An artificial kidney hemodialysis, a filtration device that filters water and supplies powerful fluid for the human body, several dozen autoclaves, a cardiomonitor, and a dental complex were commissioned [7, B. 374-375].

By 2000, the number of rural ambulatory clinics was 111, the number of paramedics-midwifery centers was 548, and the number of rural medical centers was 100 [8, B. 582-583]. By 2005, the number of medical institutions in the region was 90, and 87 of these institutions operated from the budget and 8 from non-state funds. The number of beds for patients in regional hospitals was 84.25, and 43.7 beds for every 10,000 people. Also, in 2005, 360 doctor's outpatient clinics, polyclinic institutions and 190 village doctor's offices served to protect the health of the population [9, B. 114].

In 2005, 4,020 doctors and 18,073 secondary medical workers worked in the treatment and prevention institutions of the Regional Health Department, 587 of them were high-class specialists. In 2005, 1 billion 92 million soums worth of medical equipment and apparatus were brought for the purpose of developing the material and technical base of healthcare institutions [10, B. 74]. One of the main issues identified in the program for the provision of guaranteed free medical services to the population is the provision of emergency medical care (EMS). For this purpose, in 2000, a 30-bed Emergency Department was opened in Kumkurgan district. In order to create favorable conditions for the treatment of rural residents, 115-bed day hospitals were established under the ambulatory polyclinic [11, B. 216].

In 2010-2015, the district hospital was fully equipped with modern medical equipment developed by countries such as Japan, Korea, Germany, USA, France, and Russia[12], the qualifications of medical staff were regularly improved, and new types of treatment were introduced.

The district medical association has 1 central hospital, 1 multidisciplinary central polyclinic, 2 regional departments of polyclinics and 21 rural medical centers [12]. In cooperation with the district administration, women's committee, medical association, the district department of the "Healthy generation" foundation, in order to reduce the incidence of diseases among women of child-bearing age living in rural areas, mobile medical examinations were conducted at community gatherings. 21 roundtables were organized in 28 community meetings on the prevention of disability, reduction of congenital and hereditary diseases, and preventive propaganda work was carried out among 1568 residents. In order to prevent hereditary diseases, seminars were organized in 21 general secondary schools and 2 specialized boarding schools, and explanatory work was carried out by doctors [13].

In 2017-2019, with the decision to improve the development of the private sector of the health care system, the types of medical specialties that private medical institutions can practice in our country have been increased from 50 to 126. In particular, a private joint medical clinic with the Indian state was established in the Kumkurgan district [14, B. 171].

These huge reforms in Coxa are aimed at further strengthening the health of our people, and these reforms will certainly continue consistently in the future.

Summary. In conclusion, the reforms and changes implemented in the healthcare system are aimed at improving the quality of public health and medical services in all regions of the country, and targeted state programs in this regard serve to develop the sector. The reforms implemented in the field of social life are bearing fruit.

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